

Effectiveness of Chief Minister’s Roadmap Reforms in Education on Learning of Head Teachers and Teachers

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Abstract Punjab Government of Pakistan under the headship of the Chief Minister’s has taken many moves for the promotion of education. Therefore, “Assessing effectiveness of quality enhancement measures in chief minister’s roadmap; perception of headteachers and teachers” were investigated in this study. The objective was to check the effectiveness of CM roadmap indicators on Quality Education. Taking district Sahiwal of Panjab Pakistan, as population, 300 teachers and headteachers of school side were selected as sample of study. A multi-stage convenient sampling technique was used to collect data. It was concluded that CM road map indicators does not have any statistically significant difference in teacher’s gender but have statistically significant difference on urban-rural teachers of district Sahiwal. By analysis of variance technique it has been finally concluded that CM road map indicators have substantial effect on quality education. The study opens the doors for future researcher to further evaluate other indicators except quality.

Key Words
Chief Minister (CM) Road Map. District Education Officer(DEO), PST, EST,SST,

Introduction

Teacher training refers to the strategies, measures, and establishment designed to equip (prospective) teachers with the familiarity, attitudes, behaviors, and skills they require to perform their responsibilities effectively in the classroom, school, and wider communal. Teacher’s education programs aim to promote or improve production together with consistent practical and theoretical curriculum models.(Suzie and John, 2018)

With the overview of continuous professional development (CPD) as a model for teachers in 2006, Punjab attendant as the first province spoke of its short-comings in-service educator training system. (Fraser, Carroll, McKinney, & Reid, 2006).

The chief minister, in December 2010 approved a roadmap for the betterment of schools in Punjab. The government of Punjab (Pakistan) merely takes accountability for pervading quality teaching for all concerning. The initial footsteps for teachers improved student’s background ascendancy and distinction in education. This comes under a “Road Map”.(Chief Minister Road Map, 2010) Elementary education is quite indispensable for society and the state. Elementary education cannot be acceptable in a plain article. This study is related to discussion of significance of elementary education in Pakistan. Sultana, Nargis 2001). Though this is not a matter of apprehension of higher education to be resolved. Higher education initially begins when you finish high school. Thus if government is endorsing only higher education it means it is not taking a step towards revamping the status of child for HEC is only concerning colleges. That is the main dissimilarity between significance of higher and primary education Madhavi et al. (2017).

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the current study were :

1. To investigate the problems in implementing road map indicators?
2. To find out the measures to improve quality education by road map indicators?

Research Hypothesis

This study will examine the following unsound hypothesis:

1. **H1:** There was no statistically significant difference in the teacher's role and road map indicators.
2. **H2:** There was no statistically significant difference in the residential area of teacher and road map indicators.

Review of Related Literature

Mian Muhammad Shehbaz Sharif was born on 23 September 1951. He has been the current Chief Minister of Punjab since 8 June 2013. Historically speaking, Mian Shehbaz Sharif is the province's longest-serving Chief Minister. In 1999 Shehbaz Sharif was sent in exile in Saudi Arabia. He resumed to Pakistan in 2007. Shehbaz Sharif was appointed Chief Minister for a second term in 2008. In 2013 he was nominated as Chief Minister of Punjab for a third span. His political career and services are a matter of achievements and otherwise.

Chief Minister's School Reforms Roadmap (2010)

The central idea of the newly proposed landmark program of school reforms is 'Parho Punjab, Barho Punjab'. It seems that it will be a key to a prosperous society. The School Reforms Roadmap (2010) beyond any doubt will pave the way to human development and economic growth. The Chief Minister of Punjab (Pakistan) approved a Roadmap in December 2010 to improve schools in the Province. To achieve this target, the chief minister himself started the enrollment campaign by assigning the admission form of two children. Furthermore, to enhance quality education, every schoolchild will be bound to secure at least 85% in examination.

According to Barber (2013), there is an improvement in students' as well as teachers' attendance after implementation of this roadmap which is from 81% and 83% to 92%. He claimed that 1.5million children have been enrolled as a result of the roadmap implementation (Educational Reforms:

It is a fact that School Reforms Roadmap Programme by the Chief Minister of Punjab is an objective-based programme. The following are the four main objectives of the School Reforms Roadmap Programme by the Chief Minister Punjab:

Objective 1: to ensure high-quality teaching and learning in every classroom

Objective 2: to improve leadership and accountability at all levels

Objective 3: to Support with high-quality school infrastructure

Objective 4: to Enable a conducive learning environment for students

Some striking features of Chief Minister's School Developments Roadmap (2010) are given below as exposed in the re-launching ceremony at Lahore in March 2015:

- Get out-of-school children back in schools.
- Achieve 100% enrollment of children at school.
- Equip the schools with modern educational facilities.
- Provide all financial aids to the school students to carry on their education.

Research Methodology

Survey-based detailed information was figured about perception of headteachers and teachers. All the teachers and headteachers at primary and elementary schools of district Sahiwal (Panjab Pakistan) shaped the population of the present study. There were 984 male and female Government schools registered in Sahiwal. A multi-stage sampling technique was used. From 984 primary and elementary schools, total 197 schools were selected conveniently. From 197 schools the teachers were nominated as respondent of the study. Total 300 Head Teachers and Teachers were selected for study. Self-constructed questionnaires, containing 40 items were arranged, translated into Urdu for the ease of respondents to sound understanding of the items and administered on sample of 40 respondents primarily for pilot study. The built-in final questionnaire comprised of 40 items. Concerns of supervisor and consultancy of other experts in the relevant field were also sustained for the content validity of tool. For reliability analysis Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was computed through SPSS version 16 which was found to be 0.87 that pointed towards the tool was trustworthy for the data assembling. The final questionnaire contained 34 restricted response items. After data collection, data analysis was made using the same SPSS version 16.

Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential procedures such as frequency, percentage, and t-test were used for data analysis and to test the hypothesis.

Frequency Distribution**Sample Distribution of Data**

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of the respondents.

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Responses of Sample

Sr #	Statement	S.D	D	N	A	S.A
1	Lesson plans are helping teachers in achieving quality education	0 (0)	7 (2.3)	12 (4.0)	180 (60)	101 (30)
2	Lesson planning help teachers to teach relevant content to the students	2 (0.7)	12 (4.0)	22 (7.3)	151 (50.3)	113 (30.7)
3	Teachers plan their lessons regularly	4 (1.3)	46 (15.3)	42 (14.0)	160 (53.3)	48 (16.0)
4	Lesson plans are helpful in proper utilization of time	3 (1.0)	11 (3.7)	16 (5.0)	151 (50.3)	119 (39.7)
5	Lesson planning helps them in completing syllabus in time	3 (1.0)	15 (5.0)	6 (2.0)	173 (57.7)	103 (34.3)
6	Lesson planning make learning convenient for students	3 (1.0)	4 (1.3)	3 (1.0)	166 (55.3)	101 (33.7)
7	Primary teachers are getting benefits from teachers guide	4 (1.3)	24 (8.0)	15 (5.0)	152 (50.7)	105 (35.0)
8	Use of teachers' guides helps teachers in teaching different concepts	2 (0.7)	3 (1.0)	14 (4.7)	173 (57.7)	108 (36.0)
9	Use of teachers' guides makes teaching and learning process comprehensive	3 (1.0)	9 (3.0)	14 (4.7)	153 (51.0)	121 (40.3)
10	Teachers' guide helps teachers' in time management	4 (1.3)	4 (1.3)	15 (5.0)	188 (62.7)	89 (29.7)
11	Teachers' guide presents variety of activities	15 (5.0)	13 (4.3)	173 (57.7)	99 (33.0)	11 (3.7)
12	Use of teachers' guide helps in updating the teaching skills	0 (0)	11 (3.7)	14 (4.7)	186 (62.0)	89 (29.7)
13	Use of teachers' guides is compulsory to achieve educational targets of CM road map	3 (0.7)	22 (7.3)	43 (14.3)	186 (61.0)	50 (16.7)
14	Monthly tests assess student's knowledge in proper way	2 (0.7)	17 (7.0)	6 (2.0)	162 (54.0)	113 (37.7)
15	Monthly tests inspire better learning environment	0 (0)	18 (6.0)	29 (9.7)	137 (45.7)	116 (38.7)
16	Monthly tests promote creativity among the students	1 (0.3)	13 (4.3)	40 (13.3)	137 (45.7)	109 (36.3)
17	Monthly tests help teachers in promoting learning abilities among	2 (0.7)	7 (2.3)	20 (6.7)	168 (56.0)	103 (34.3)

18	Monthly tests help teachers in finding out the weak areas of students	1 (0.3)	4 (1.3)	14 (4.7)	155 (51.7)	126 (42.0)
19	Monthly tests help students in overcoming the weakness well in time	0 (0)	6 (2.0)	8 (2.7)	154 (54.3)	132 (42.0)
20	Monthly tests promote positive competition among students	0 (0)	1 (0.3)	29 (9.7)	138 (46.0)	132 (42.0)
21	Monthly tests are helpful in achieving the better results	0 (0)	8 (2.7)	30 (10.0)	143 (47.7)	119 (39.7)
22	PEC exams compel thorough teaching on the part of teachers	8 (2.7)	23 (7.7)	33 (11.0)	176 (58.7)	60 (20.0)
23	PEC exams objectively evaluate student' performance	10 (3.3)	29 (9.7)	56 (18.7)	153 (51.0)	52 (17.3)
24	PEC exams enhancing quality education	20 (6.7)	50 (16.7)	41 (30.7)	132 (42.0)	57 (19.0)
25	PEC exams are a helpful source of examining students' achievements	21 (7.0)	39 (13.0)	37 (12.3)	148 (49.3)	55 (18.3)
26	PEC exams are source to promote healthy compaction among students	13 (4.3)	37 (12.3)	19 (6.3)	168 (56.0)	63 (21.0)
27	Teachers trainings are helpful in polishing hidden abilities of teachers	12 (4.0)	29 (9.7)	18 (6.0)	151 (50.3)	90 (30.0)
28	Teachers training program introduce teacher new teaching techniques	11 (3.7)	32 (10.7)	14 (4.7)	179 (59.7)	64 (21.3)
29	Under supervision of master trainers teachers learn to solve class room problem	6 (2.0)	33 (11.0)	23 (7.7)	171 (57.0)	67 (22.3)
30	Teacher trainings enhance time management	10 (3.3)	36 (12.0)	31 (10.3)	146 (48.7)	77 (27.7)
31	Science and IT labs enhance quality education	6 (2.0)	23 (7.0)	19 (6.3)	147 (49.0)	105 (35.0)
32	Students get better learning by performing practical's in labs	0 (0)	16 (5.3)	24 (8.0)	135 (45.0)	125 (41.7)
33	Learning by creating educational skills among the students	0 (0)	14 (4.7)	13 (4.3)	149 (49.7)	124 (41.3)
34	Labs are the utmost need of the time in the present age of science	1 (0.3)	10 (3.3)	21 (7.0)	104 (34.7)	164 (54.7)

Inferential Analysis

In this section, testing of the null hypothesis is represented. For this purpose researcher formulated 12 hypotheses. By using IBM SPSS 21, data were analyzed. At 5% level of significance, the entire hypotheses were showed.

Lesson Planning and Teacher's Role

In order to “what was the role of teacher's difference and lesson planning” the researcher used a t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho1: There was a statistically insignificant difference in teacher's role and lesson planning.

The following table exhibited the gender difference of sample.

Table 2. Lesson Planning and Teacher's Role

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	24.8000	3.04772	.24885	0.280	0.201
Female	150	24.7067	2.71843	.22196		

In table 2 the value of $t=0.280$ and significant difference is 0.201 explained that there was insignificant difference and, therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in teacher's role and lesson planning) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that male and female teachers had comparable levels of lesson planning.

Teachers Guide and Teacher's Role

In order to “what was the role of teacher difference and teachers guide” the researcher used a t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho2: There was a statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and teacher guide.

The following table exhibited the gender difference of the sample.

Table 3. Teachers Guide and Teacher's Role

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	29.0267	3.01216	.24594	-0.790	0.434
Female	150	29.0533	2.80887	.22934		

In table 3 the value of $t= -0.790$ and significant difference is 0.434 explained that there was an insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and teachers guide) was failed to be rejected saying that gender of teacher had comparable effect on lesson planning.

Monthly Test and Teacher's Role

In order to “what was the role of teacher difference and monthly test” the researcher used a t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho3: There was a statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and monthly test.

The following table exhibited the gender difference of the sample.

Table 4. Monthly test and Teacher's role

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	34.4533	3.95034	.32254	1.850	0.891
Female	150	33.5933	4.09796	.33460		

In table 4 the value of $t=1.850$ and significant difference is 0.891 explained that there was an insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and monthly test) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that the gender of the teacher had comparable effect on monthly test.

PEC Examination and Teacher's Role

In order to “what was the role of teacher gender difference and PEC Exam” the researcher used a t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho4: There was a statistically insignificant difference in teacher gender and PEC exams.

The following table exhibited the gender difference of sample.

Table 5. PEC Examination and Teacher's Role

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	18.5600	4.06900	.33223	0.531	0.551
Female	150	18.3000	4.34695	.35493		

In table 5 the value of $t=0.531$ and significant difference is 0.551 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in teacher gender and PEC Exam) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that the gender of teacher had a comparable effect on PEC Exam.

Teachers' Training Program and Teacher's Role

In order to “what was the role of teacher difference and teachers training program” the researcher used a t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho5: There was a statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and teacher training program.

The following table exhibited the gender difference of the sample.

Table 6. Teachers Training Program and Teacher's Role

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	15.3333	3.70501	.30251	-0.584	0.76
Female	150	15.5667	3.19273	.26069		

In table 6 the value of $t=-0.531$ and significant difference is 0.76 explained that there was an insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and teachers training program) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that the gender of the teacher had comparable effect on teachers' training program.

Labs Practices and Teacher's Role

In order to “what was the role of teacher gender difference and Labs practice” the researcher used a t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho6: There statistically insignificant difference in teacher role and lab practice.

The following table exhibited the gender difference of the sample.

Table 7. Lab Practices and Teacher's Role

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	17.2600	2.36141	.19281	1.936	0.55
Female	150	16.7000	2.64131	.21566		

In table 7 the value of $t= 1.94$ and significant difference is 0.55 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in teacher gender and labs practice) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that gender of teacher had comparable effect on labs practice.

Lesson Planning and Residential area of Teacher's

In order to “what was the role of residential area of teachers and Lesson planning” the researcher used t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho7: There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Lesson planning.

Following table exhibited the residential difference of sample.

Table 8. Lesson Planning and Residential Area

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	24.8000	2.76362	.22565	0.280	0.399
Female	150	24.7067	3.00681	.24550		

In table 8 the value of $t= 0.280$ and significant difference is 0.399 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and

Lesson planning) was failed to be rejected.
Saying that Locality of teacher had comparable effect on lesson planning.

Teacher guide and Residential area of Teacher's

In order to “what was the role of residential area of teachers and Teachers guide” the researcher used t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho8: There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Teachers guide.

Following table exhibited the residential difference of sample.

Table 9. Teachers Guide and Residential Area

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	29.1467	2.87873	.23505	0.634	0.545
Female	150	28.9333	2.94164	.24018		

In table 9 the value of $t = 0.634$ and significant difference is 0.545 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Teachers guide) was failed to be rejected. Saying that Locality of teacher had comparable effect on Teachers guide.

Monthly test and Residential area of Teacher's

In order to “what was the role of residential area of teachers and Monthly test” the researcher used t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho9: There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Monthly test.

Following table exhibited the residential difference of sample.

Table 10. Monthly Test and Residential Area

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	33.5200	3.97934	.32491	-2.17	0.733
Female	150	34.5267	4.05283	.33091		

In table 10 the value of $t = -2.17$ and significant difference is 0.733 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Monthly test) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that Locality of teacher had comparable effect on Monthly test.

PEC Exam and Teacher's Residential Area

In order to “what was the role of residential area of teachers and PEC Exam” the researcher used t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho10: There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and PEC Exam.

The following table exhibited the residential difference of sample.

Table 11. PEC Exam and Residential Area

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	18.2667	4.19118	.34221	-0.672	0.612
Female	150	18.5933	4.22695	.34513		

In table 11 the value of $t = -0.672$ and significant difference is 0.612 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was a statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and PEC exam) was failed to be rejected.

Saying that the Locality of teacher had comparable effect on PEC Exam.

Teachers' Training program and Teacher's Residential Area

In order to “what was the role of the residential area of teachers and Teachers training program” the researcher used t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

Ho11: There statistically insignificant difference in the residential area of teachers and Teachers' training programs. The following table exhibited the residential difference of sample.

Table 12. Teachers' Training program and Residential Area

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	15.4133	3.34621	.27322	-0.84	0.56
Female	150	15.4867	3.57045	.29153		

In table 12 the value of $t = -0.84$ and significant difference is 0.56 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Teachers training program) was failed to be rejected. Saying that Locality of teacher had comparable effect on Teachers training program.

Lab practices and Residential area of Teacher's

In order to "what was the role of residential area of teachers and Lab practices" the researcher used t-test (with 0.05 as a significance level) for the following hypothesis.

H12: There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Lab practices.

Following table exhibited the residential difference of sample.

Table 13. Lab practices and Residential Area

SEX	N	Average	STD	STDE Mean	T	P
Male	150	16.8200	2.66740	.21779	-1.02	0.051
Female	150	17.1400	2.35458	.19225		

In table 13 the value of $t = -1.02$ and significant difference is 0.051 explained that there was insignificant difference and therefore, the null hypothesis (There was statistically insignificant difference in residential area of teachers and Lab practices) failed to be rejected saying that Locality of teacher had a comparable effect on Lab practices.

Conclusion

This study intended to investigate the effect of "Assessing Effectiveness of quality enhancement measures in the chief minister's roadmap: perception of headteachers and teachers" of district Sahiwal teachers. The present study concluded that Quality Education was affected by teachers' training and lab practices. The teacher training and lab practices were found to be alike among gender and residential area.

This study uses the multiple linear regression model to measure the effect of CM road map indicators on Quality Education and found that in a monthly test, PEC exam, teacher guides, and labs have a considerably positive effect on Quality Education. While lesson planning and teacher training have considerable negative impact on Quality Education.

Recommendations

In the background of the present research and its findings, the following are the recommendation need to be considered for further research.

- The Punjab Education Commission Examination may be compulsory for private sectors. It may boost a healthy and constructive competition between private and govt. sector.
- The investigation on the same topic as well as the qualitative approach of study may be conducted in other districts of the Punjab Pakistan, to find out effectiveness of Punjab Government's policies regarding student performance and achievement at secondary level.

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Questionnaire:

1. NAME: _____
2. School Name: _____
3. Designation/Scale: _____
4. Urban/Rural: _____
5. Gender: _____
6. Experience: _____
7. Qualification: _____
8. Professional Qualification: _____

9. Lesson plans are helping teachers in achieving quality education
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

10. Lesson planning help teachers in teaching relevant content to the students
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

11. Teachers plan their lessons regularly
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

12. Lesson plans are helpful in proper utilization of time
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

13. Lesson planning helps teachers in completing syllabus in time
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

14. Lesson planning make learning convenient for students
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

15. Primary teachers are getting benefits from teachers' guide
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral

- d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
16. Use of teachers' guides help teachers in teaching different concepts
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
17. Use of teachers' guides make teaching and learning process comprehensive
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
18. Teachers guide help time management
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
19. Teachers' guide present Variety of activities
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
20. Use of teachers' guide helps teachers in updating the teaching skills
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
21. Use of teachers guides is compulsory to achieve educational targets of CM road map
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
22. Monthly tests assess student's knowledge in proper way
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
23. Monthly tests inspire better learning environment
- a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree

- e) Strongly Agree
- 24. Monthly tests promote creativity among the students
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 25. Monthly tests help promoting learning abilities among the students
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 26. Monthly tests find out students' weak areas
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 27. Monthly tests overcome the students' weakness well in time
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 28. Monthly tests promote positive competition among students
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 29. Monthly tests are helpful in achieving the better results
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 30. PEC exams compel thorough teaching on the part of teachers
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree
- 31. PEC exams objectively evaluate student' performance
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

32. PEC exams enhance quality education
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

33. PEC exams are a helpful source of examining students achievements
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

34. PEC exams are a source to promote healthy compaction among students
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

35. Teachers trainings are helpful in polishing hidden abilities of teachers
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

36. Teachers' training program introduce teachers with new teaching techniques
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

37. Under supervision of master trainers teachers learn to solve class room problems
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree

38. Teacher trainings enhance time management
 - a) Strongly Disagree
 - b) Disagree
 - c) Neutral
 - d) Agree
 - e) Strongly Agree